

Based on literature review, no HPLC methods were available for quantification⁴ of cabotegravir and rilpivirine in pharmaceutical dosage forms. So, keeping this point into consideration we attempt this work to develop and validate the RP-HPLC method within short retention time.

II. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

A. MATERIALS:

Rilpivirine and Cabotegravir pure drugs (API), Combination Rilpivirine¹ and Cabotegravir⁸ injection (Cabenuva), Distilled water, Acetonitrile, Phosphate buffer, Methanol, Potassium dehydrogenate ortho phosphate buffer, Ortho-phosphoric acid. All the above chemicals and solvents are from Rankem.

B. INSTRUMENTS:

UV-VIS spectrophotometer PG Instruments T60 with special bandwidth of 2 mm and 10 mm and matched quartz cells integrated with UV win 6 Software. Electronic Balance-Denver, p^H meter -BVK enterprises, Ultrasonicator-BVK enterprises, WATERS HPLC 2695 SYSTEM equipped with quaternary pumps, Photo Diode Array detector and Auto sampler integrated with Empower 2 Software.

III. METHOD DEVELOPMENT

PREPARATION OF DILUENT: Methanol and Water in the ratio of 50:50.

0.1% OPA BUFFER: 1ml of orthophosphoric acid solution was diluted to 1000 ml with Milli-Q water.

PREPARATION OF STANDARD STOCK:

Accurately Weighed and transferred 75 mg of Rilpivirine, and 50 mg of Cabotegravir⁸ working Standards into 50 ml clean dry volumetric flasks, 10 ml of diluent, sonicated for 10 minutes and made up to the final volume with diluents. (1500µg/ml Rilpivirine, and 1000 µg/ml of Cabotegravir. 1ml of filtered sample stock solution was transferred to 10ml volumetric flask and made up with diluent with final concentrations of 150 µg/ml Rilpivirine, and 100 µg/ml of Cabotegravir).

PREPARATION OF SAMPLE STOCK SOLUTIONS:

Pipetted out 1 ml of Rilpivirine and Cabotegravir injection sample into a 100 ml volumetric flask, 50 ml of diluents was added and sonicated for 25 min, further the volume was made up with diluent and filtered by HPLC filters. (3000 µg/ml Rilpivirine, and 2000 µg/ml of Cabotegravir).

PREPARATION OF SAMPLE WORKING SOLUTIONS (100% SOLUTION): 0.5 ml of filtered sample stock solution was transferred to 10 ml volumetric flask and made up with diluent. (150 µg/ml Rilpivirine, and 100 µg/ml of Cabotegravir)

IV. VALIDATION

A. PRECISION:

From a single volumetric flask of working standard solution six injections were given and the obtained areas were mentioned above. Average area, standard deviation and % RSD were calculated for two drugs.

B. LINEARITY:

Six linearity concentrations 0.25 ml, 0.5 ml, 0.75 ml, 1.0 ml, 1.25 ml, 1.5 ml each of the two standard stock solutions were pipetted out and made up to 10 ml with concentrations of 37.5 µg/ml of Rip and 25 µg/ml of Cab, 75 µg/ml of Ril and 50 µg/ml of Cab, 112.5 µg/ml of Ril and 75 µg/ml of Cab, 150 µg/ml of Ril and 100 µg/ml of Cab, 187.5 µg/ml of Ril and 125 µg/ml of Cab, 187.5 µg/ml

of Ril and 125 µg/ml of Cab, 150 µg/ml of Ril and 150 µg/ml of Cab .respectively, linearity equation and Correlation coefficient were obtained.

C. ACCURACY:

Three levels of Accuracy samples 50% 100% 150% were prepared by standard addition method. Triplicate injections were given for each level of accuracy and mean, % Recovery was obtained.

D. ROBUSTNESS.

Robustness conditions like Flow minus (0.9 ml/min), Flow plus (1.1 ml/min), mobile phase minus, mobile phase plus, temperature minus (25°C) and temperature plus(35°C) were maintained, and samples were injected in duplicate manner. System suitability parameters were checked as per ICH guidelines

E. LOD SAMPLE PREPARATION

0.25 ml each from two standard stock solutions was pipetted out and transferred to two separate 10 ml volumetric flasks and made up with diluents. From the above solutions 0.1 ml each of Rilpivirine, Cabotegravir, solutions respectively were transferred to 10 ml volumetric flasks and made up with the same diluents

F. LOQ SAMPLE PREPARATION

0.25 ml each from two standard stock solutions was pipetted out and transferred to two separate 10 ml volumetric flasks and made up with diluent. From the above solutions 0.3 ml each of Rilpivirine, Cabotegravir, and solutions respectively were transferred to 10ml volumetric flasks and made up with the same diluent.

G. DEGRADATION STUDIES:

standards and degraded samples are injected and calculated the percentage of drug degraded in solution by applying different conditions like acid, alkali, and oxidative, photolytic, thermal, and neutral analysis

V. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Optimized Chromatographic conditions:

Mobile phase: 50% OPA: 50% Acetonitrile

Flow rate: 1 ml/min, Column temperature: 30°C

Column: Kromasil C18 (4.6 x 150 mm, 5 µm) , Detector wavelength: 257.0 nm

Column temperature: 30°C, Injection volume :10 µL

Run time: 10 min. Diluent: Water and Acetonitrile in the ratio 50:50

Results: Both peaks have good resolution, tailing Factor, theoretical plate count and resolution.

Fig 2. Optimized Chromatogram

Fig 3. Typical Chromatogram

A. SPECIFICITY:

Retention times of Rilpivirine and Cabotegravir were 2.342 min and 3.350 min respectively. We did not find and interfering peaks in blank and placebo at retention times of these drugs in this method. So, this method was said to be specific.

B. LINEARITY:

Six linear concentrations of Rilpivirine (12.5- 75 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) and Cabotegravir (6.25-37.5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) were injected in a duplicate manner. Average areas were mentioned above, and linearity equations obtained for Rilpivirine was $y = 29602x + 20224$.and of Cabotegravir was $y = 24752x + 4467$. Correlation coefficient obtained was 0.999 for both drugs.

Fig 4. Calibration curve of Rilpivirine

Fig 5. Calibration curve of Cabotegravir

C. PRECISION:

From a single volumetric flask of working standard solution six injections were given and the obtained areas were mentioned above. Average area, standard deviation and % RSD were calculated for two drugs. % RSD obtained as 0.6% and 0.3% respectively for Rilpivirine and Cabotegravir. As

the limit of Precision was less than “2” the system precision was passed in this method.

Table:1 precision table for Rilpivirine and Cabotegravir

S. No	Area of Rilpivirine	Area of Cabotegravir
1.	4397051	2479452
2.	4468613	2497679
3.	4398535	2480996
4.	4445219	2494550
5.	4411805	2483419
6.	4416803	2497913
Mean	4423004	2489002
S. D	28319.1	8624.9
%RSD	0.6	0.3

D. ACCURACY

Three levels of Accuracy samples were prepared by standard addition method. Triplicate injections were given for each level of accuracy and mean %Recovery was obtained as 100.52% and 99.81% for Rilpivirine and Cabotegravir respectively.

Table 2: Accuracy table of Cabotegravir

% Level	Amount Spiked ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Amount recovered ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	% Recovery	Mean %Recovery
50%	75	75.2	100.3	100.52%
	75	76.0	101.4	
	75	74.7	99.6	
100%	150	152.4	101.6	
	150	150.1	100.1	
	150	149.0	99.3	
150%	225	229.2	101.9	
	225	226.5	100.7	
	225	224.7	99.9	

Table 3: Accuracy table of Rilpivirine

% Level	Amount Spiked ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Amount recovered ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	% Recovery	Mean %Recovery
50%	50	49.25	98.50	99.81%
	50	49.57	99.13	
	50	50.19	100.38	
100%	100	100.20	99.80	
	100	100.05	0.56	
	100	99.16	0.56	
150%	150	151.72	101.14	
	150	150.20	100.13	
	150	150.20	99.6	

Table: 4 Sensitivity table of Rilpivirine and Cabotegravir

Molecule	LOD ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	LOQ ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)
Rilpivirine	0.37	1.13
Cabotegravir	0.53	1.61

ROBUSTNESS:

Robustness conditions like Flow minus (0.9ml/min), Flow plus (1.1ml/min), mobile phase minus (55B:45A), mobile phase plus (45B:55A), temperature minus (25°C) and temperature plus(35°C) were maintained, and samples were injected in duplicate manner. System suitability parameters were not much affected, and all the parameters were passed. %RSD was within the limits

Table: 5 Robustness data for Rilpivirine and Cabotegravir.

S.no	Condition	%RSD of Rilpivirine	%RSD of Cabotegravir
1	Flow rate (-) 0.9ml/min	0.2	0.3
2	Flow rate (+) 1.1ml/min	1.4	1.3
3	Mobile phase (-) 55B:45A	0.2	0.6
4	Mobile phase (+) 45B:55A	1.4	1.1
5	Temperature (-) 25°C	0.3	0.2
6	Temperature (+) 35°C	0.2	0.7

SYSTEM SUITABILITY: All the system suitability parameters were within the range and satisfactory as per ICH guidelines.

Table: 6 System suitability parameters for Cabotegravir and Rilpivirine

S no	Rilpivirine			Cabotegravir			Resolution	
	Inj	RT (min)	USP Plate Count	Tailing	RT (min)	USP Plate Count		Tailing
1		2.340	2772	1.55	3.348	3258	1.47	4.7
2		2.341	2743	1.55	3.349	3286	1.46	4.8
3		2.342	2807	1.54	3.35	3318	1.45	4.8
4		2.346	2855	1.52	3.355	3175	1.45	4.7
5		2.349	2896	1.53	3.362	3248	1.46	4.7
6		2.349	2889	1.54	3.363	3235	1.47	4.7

Fig 6. System suitability Chromatogram

ASSAY:

Rhodes pharmaceuticals, bearing the label claim Rilpivirine 50mg, Cabotegravir 25mg. Assay was performed with the above formulation. Average % Assay for Rilpivirine and Cabotegravir obtained was 99.93% and 100.14% respectively.

Table:7 Assay Data of Rilpivirine

S.no	Standard Area	Sample area	% Assay
1	4397051	4425292	99.95
2	4468613	4434932	100.17
3	4398535	4421615	99.87
4	4445219	4445716	100.41
5	4411805	4417734	99.78
6	4416803	4401704	99.42
Avg	4423004	4424499	99.93
SD	28319.1	15055.4	0.34
%RSD	0.6	0.3	0.3

Table:8 Assay data of Cabotegravir

S.no	Standard Area	Sample area	% Assay
1	2479452	2481979	99.62
2	2497679	2482518	99.64
3	2480996	2494539	100.12
4	2494550	2502932	100.46
5	2483419	2505622	100.57
6	2497913	2501772	100.41
Avg	2489002	2494894	100.14
SD	8624.9	10460.4	0.42
%RSD	0.3	0.4	0.42

DEGRADATION STUDIES:

standards and degraded samples are injected and calculated the percentage of drug degraded in solution by applying different conditions like acid, alkali, and oxidative, photolytic, thermal, and neutral analysis.

Table: 9 Degradation studies

Type of degradation	Rilpivirine			Cabotegravir		
	AREA	%RECOVERED	%DEGRADED	AREA	%RECOVERED	%DEGRADED
Acid	4132237	93.33	6.67	2334616	93.70	6.30
Base	4226097	95.45	4.55	2381169	95.57	4.43
Peroxide	4218800	95.29	4.71	2379279	95.50	4.50
Thermal	4368187	98.66	1.34	2454203	98.50	1.50
UV	4386204	99.07	0.93	2463867	98.89	1.11
Water	4404421	99.48	0.52	2486348	99.79	0.21

CONCLUSION

An effective, simple, Accurate, precise method was developed for the simultaneous estimation of the Rilpivirine and Cabotegravir in pharmaceutical (injection) dosage form. The Retention time of Rilpivirine and Cabotegravir were found to be 2.349 min and 3.363 min. %RSD of the Rilpivirine and Cabotegravir were found to be 0.6 and 0.3 respectively. %Recovery was obtained as 99.94% and 98.69% for Rilpivirine and Cabotegravir respectively. LOD and LOQ values obtained from regression equations of Rilpivirine and Cabotegravir were 0.37, 0.53 and 1.13, 1.61 respectively. The regression equation of Rilpivirine is $y = 29602x + 20224$ and $y = 24752x + 4467$ of Cabotegravir. Retention times were decreased, and that run time was decreased, so the method developed was simple and economical that can be adopted in regular Quality control test in Industries.

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